

Studies on Complexes of Tartaric Acid. II. Reaction of Potassium Antimony(III) Tartrate with a Strong Acid Ion Exchanger in Hydrogen Form

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Manuscript received 15 January 1974; accepted 5 June 1974

The interaction of potassium antimony (III) tartrate (KSbT) with a strong acid ion exchanger in hydrogen form was studied in detail. About 30% of the complex undergoes hydrolysis liberating an equivalent amount of tartaric acid. The effluent was a mixture of HSbT and tartaric acid and the extent of hydrolysis was found to be independent of the concentration of KSbT solution passed through the ion exchanger.

In a recent communication¹ from this laboratory studies on potassium antimony(III) tartrate (KSbT) have been reported, where it was shown that potassium antimony (III) tartrate does not contain a free COOH group. Banerji and Chari² have interpreted the *pH* and conductometric titration data for the effluent obtained by passing a solution of KSbT through a column of Amberlite IR-120H in terms of dimerisation of the monomeric complex assuming the structure of the latter to be the one reported by Grdenic and Kamenar³ containing a free COOH group. Addition of potassium hydroxide in equimolar proportion to a solution of KSbT results in the decomposition of the complex into Sb₂O₃ and dipotassium tartrate. Hence if HSbT is titrated with KOH, one would expect the formation of Sb₂O₃ and dipotassium tartrate on the addition of 2 moles of KOH per mole of HSbT. During our attempts to prepare HSbT by passing a solution of KSbT through a column of Dowex 50H development of a white band was observed. Also, the total antimony content in the effluent was found to be lower than that in the original solution. In view of these discrepancies it was considered worthwhile to investigate the hydrolytic decomposition of the complex on an ion exchanger bed.

Experimental

The preparation of potassium antimony(III) tartrate was carried out as reported earlier¹. All other reagents used were of analytical reagent grade.

Ion exchange experiments were carried out using Dowex 50 and Amberlite IR 120 resins. A known volume of a standard solution of the complex (60 to 100 ml of 0.01 to 0.2M solutions were used in different experiments—Table 1) was passed through a column of

the resin in hydrogen form and the effluent was collected. The column was then washed with water till the effluent was neutral. The total effluent was made up to 250 ml and the antimony content was determined by iodimetric titration⁴. 25 ml of this solution was diluted to 100 ml for carrying out *pH* titrations.

The antimony present in the column was eluted with 3N HCl and the antimony content in the effluent was determined as before. The potassium content was estimated gravimetrically as K₂SO₄⁴ in the filtrate after precipitating antimony as sulfide from the effluent.

pH titrations were carried out with a Beckman model G *pH* meter using glass electrode and calomel reference electrode at 25° ± 1°.

Results and Discussion

When a 0.2M solution of potassium antimony(III) tartrate was passed at a low rate (2 to 3 ml/min) through a column of Dowex 50H, development of a white band was observed. However, the effluent obtained was clear and its *pH* was found to be ~2. Approximately 150 to 200 ml water had to be passed to make the effluent neutral. Elution with 3N HCl resulted in further development of the white band which moved down and the effluent obtained initially contained white precipitate. With amberlite IR 120H the initial development of the white band could be observed only when the concentration of the solution was high (0.2M) and the flow rate was very low. On elution with HCl development of the white band was observed in all cases. These results indicate that the complex undergoes partial decomposition when passed through a column of the resin in hydrogen form. Analyses of the initial effluent as well

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF ION EXCHANGE EXPERIMENTS

Conc. of KSbT loaded (moles/liter)	Total Sb loaded (millimoles)	Total Sb in the effluent Sbe (millimoles)	Total Sb retained in the column Sbr (millimoles)	Sbe + Sbr	% Sb retained in the column
0.01	1.0	0.68	0.30	0.98	30.3
0.04	3.0	2.10	0.92	3.02	30.5
0.08	8.0	5.60	2.35	7.95	29.5
0.20	12.0	8.20	3.70	11.90	31.0

as the one obtained by elution with HCl for total antimony content show that approx. 30% of the complex decomposes and the antimony part of this is retained in the resin bed. The potassium content in the effluent obtained after elution with HCl indicates that all the potassium present in the original solution is retained in the resin bed.

The influence of concentration of KSbT solution on the extent of decomposition of the complex was studied in the concentration range 0.01 to 0.2M and the results given in Table I show that there is no appreciable variation in the degree of decomposition of the complex (% decomposition varies from 29.5 to 31) with respect to its concentration.

The first step in the reaction of the complex with the resin is expected to be

Due to the instability of the protonated complex in a strongly acidic medium, it undergoes partial decomposition.

When a 0.2M solution of the complex was passed through the column of the resin in hydrogen form, 69% of Sb was present in the effluent and the rest was retained in the resin bed. Since no tartaric acid was present in the effluent obtained by elution with 3N HCl, it is assumed that all of it is liberated as a result of the hydrolysis of the complex. The white band of antimony left in the resin bed in the column was examined and found to be Sb₂O₃.

If the decomposition of the complex on the resin bed is accompanied by the liberation of equivalent amount of tartaric acid, then for every mole of complex passed 0.69 mole of HSbT and 0.31 mole of tartaric acid should be produced. The pH titration curve for HSbT should give an inflection at m=1 (m = number of moles of alkali added per mole of metal ion) around a pH of 4.5 while for tartaric acid (H₄T) an inflection at m=2 should be obtained around a pH of 7.0. In a mixture of 0.69 mole of HSbT and 0.31 mole of tartaric acid, one would expect an inflection at m≈1.31 (0.69 + 2×0.31) (calculation of m is based on antimony content in the original solution). The titration curve obtained for the effluent is shown in Fig 1 (Curve 1A) from which it can be seen that the observed value (1.3) is very close to the expected one. To confirm whether the titration curve is for a mixture of HSbT and H₄T in the ratio 69:31, a mixture of KSbT and H₄T was prepared and the titration curve for this is shown in Fig 1 (Curve 2A). It can be seen that if the alkali equivalent to the acid required to convert KSbT to HSbT is added to the

observed values, a curve is obtained which is almost superimposable on the one obtained for the effluent from ion exchange experiments. Similar results were obtained with titrations involving KSbT concentration of 0.08M (Curves 1B and 2B, Fig 1).

Fig 1 : pH titration curves.
Curves 1A and 1B : Effluent obtained by passing 60 ml of 0.2 M KSbT and 100 ml of 0.08 M KSbT respectively.

Curves 2A and 2B : Mixtures of KSbT and H₄T with ratio of Sb to H₄T same as those expected in 1A and 1B respectively.

From the above results, the overall hydrolytic reaction may be written as

The absence of decomposition of the complex beyond 30% appears to be due to the presence of sufficient excess of complexing agent in the mixture.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Dr. M. D. Karkhanavala, Head, Chemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre for his encouragement.

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